

2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthaldehyde Chelates of Group IV Elements

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Some chelates of Group IV elements with ligand (LH) 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde— LMCl_3 ($\text{M} = \text{Ti}^{IV}$ or Si^{IV}), L_2MCl_2 ($\text{M} = \text{Ti}^{IV}$, Zr^{IV} or Sn^{IV}), $\text{L}_2\text{Sn}^{IV}\text{X}_2$ ($\text{X} = \text{Br}$ or I), $\text{LnTi}^{IV}(\text{}^i\text{OC}_3\text{H}_7)_{4-n}$ ($n = 1$ or 2) and L_2Sn^{II} — have been isolated. The chloro-chelate compounds, except the silicon compound, have been found to form adducts with ammonia and methylamine.

IN a previous communication¹, we reported isolation of some rare earth chelates with the ligand 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde. No compound of any group IV element with this ligand was come across in literature, although compounds with analogous ligand salicylaldehyde are known²⁻⁴ and this led us to undertake some work in this respect. In this note are reported some chelates of silicon(IV), titanium(IV), zirconium(IV), tin(IV) and tin(II) with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde which we have synthesized.

The various compounds synthesized and their elemental analyses are given in Table 1.

The bonding of the ligand to the metal may be written as

X = halogen alkoxy group
Y = valence of the metal
n = 1 or 2.

This is supported by the disappearance of the OH(str.) absorption band and lowering of the carbonyl stretching frequency of the ligand by 10-30 cm^{-1} in the infrared spectra of the complexes. The carbonyl frequency shift in the case of bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydato)tin(IV) dihalides depends upon the electron density of the halide substituent ($\text{Cl} > \text{Br} > \text{I}$), the frequency of the iodide compound being almost the same as that of the free ligand.

Preparation of the chelates

In the preparation of the compounds of the composition LnMCl_{4-n} ($\text{M} = \text{Ti}^{IV}$, Zr^{IV} or Si^{IV} and $n = 1$ or 2), a solution of the ligand was added dropwise to a cooled solution of the metal tetrachloride and the mixture was heated under reflux till HCl

fumes no longer evolved. The quantities of metal tetrachloride and the ligand taken were in the molar ratio of 1 : 0.8 for $n = 1$ or 1 : 2.5 for $n = 2$. The solvent medium was tetrahydrofuran in the case of zirconium compound and benzene in all other cases. The solid that precipitated out was washed with the solvent and dried at 60° *in vacuo*.

The compounds $\text{LnTi}^{IV}(\text{}^i\text{OC}_3\text{H}_7)_{4-n}$ ($n = 1$ or 2) were prepared by treating titanium tetra-isopropoxide with the ligand, taken in the respective molar ratio of 1 : n , allowing the exothermic reaction to proceed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr and distilling off the liberated alcohol at 60° under reduced pressure. The solids obtained were washed with petroleum ether before drying at room temperature *in vacuo*. Treatment of a solution of mono-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydato) titanium (IV) trichloride in isopropyl alcohol diluted with benzene, with ammonia and refluxing the same for 2 hr thereafter resulted in giving (on filtration and concentration) the compound mono(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydato) monoisopropoxy oxotitanium(IV) which was found to be a tetramer from its molecular weight.

The tin compounds $\text{L}_2\text{Sn}^{IV}\text{Cl}_2$ and L_2Sn^{II} were synthesized by gradual treatment of benzene solution of stannic or stannous chloride, as the case may be, with a suspension of sodium salt of the ligand in benzene (metal to ligand molar ratio = 1 : 2) followed by heating under reflux for a few hours and concentrating the filtered solution to the required volume. The compounds were washed with hexane before drying at 60° *in vacuo*. The sodium derivative of the ligand was obtained by treating the ligand with sodium methoxide, in equal molar ratio, in benzene, heating the mixture under reflux for 1 hr and removing the solvent plus methanol under reduced pressure. Attempts to prepare the monosubstituted compounds $\text{LSn}^{IV}\text{Cl}_3$ and LSn^{II}Cl , using equal moles of the ligand sodium salt and stannic or stannous chloride, gave only the bis-substituted compounds. Treatment of the suspension in chloroform of stannous bis-complex (at 5°-10°) dropwise with bromine or iodine solution in chloroform (complex to halogen molar ratio = 1 : 2) and continuing the stirring for some time thereafter yielded the compounds $\text{L}_2\text{Sn}^{IV}\text{Br}_2$ and $\text{L}_2\text{Sn}^{IV}\text{I}_2$. The compounds were well-washed with chloroform before drying *in vacuo* at room

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PATIL & SEN : 2-HYDROXY-1-NAPHTHALDEHYDE CHELATES OF GROUP IV ELEMENTS

TABLE 1—COMPLEXES OF GROUP IV METALS WITH 2-HYDROXY-1-NAPHTHALDEHYDE

Sr.No.	Name of the compound	Colour	Analyses %				
			Metal	Halogen	C	H	N
1.	Mono(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydato) titanium(IV) trichloride. C ₁₁ H ₇ O ₂ Cl ₃ Ti	Chocolate brown	14.61 (14.72)	33.07 (32.70)	40.80 (40.60)	2.49 (2.17)	—
1a.	-do- ammonia adduct C ₁₁ H ₇ O ₂ Cl ₃ Ti.4NH ₃	yellow	12.24 (12.17)	27.34 (27.04)	—	—	14.13 (14.23)
1b.	-do- methylamine adduct C ₁₁ H ₇ O ₂ Cl ₃ Ti.2CH ₃ NH ₂	yellow	12.47 (12.33)	27.45 (27.38)	—	—	7.27 (7.21)
2.	Bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydato)-titanium(IV) dichloride. C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₄ Cl ₂ Ti	brown	10.48 (10.39)	15.52 (15.38)	57.03 (57.28)	3.42 (3.06)	—
2a.	-do- ammonia adduct C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₄ Cl ₂ Ti.4NH ₃	yellow	9.21 (9.05)	13.26 (13.40)	—	—	10.31 (10.58)
2b.	-do- methylamine adduct C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₄ Cl ₂ Ti.2CH ₃ NH ₂	yellow	8.98 (9.13)	13.41 (13.52)	—	—	5.50 (5.34)
3.	Bis-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydato)-zirconium(IV) dichloride. C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₄ Cl ₂ Zr.	greenish	18.24 (18.08)	14.20 (14.06)	51.83 (52.37)	3.11 (2.80)	—
3a.	-do- ammonia adduct C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₄ Cl ₂ Zr.4NH ₃	yellow	15.76 (15.93)	12.57 (12.38)	—	—	9.53 (9.78)
3b.	-do- methylamine adduct C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₄ Cl ₂ Zr.2CH ₃ NH ₂	yellow	15.89 (16.07)	12.22 (12.49)	—	—	5.11 (4.94)
4.	Mono(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydato)-silicon(IV) trichloride. C ₁₁ H ₇ O ₂ Cl ₃ Si	white	9.27 (9.19)	34.70 (34.81)	—	—	—
5.	Bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydato) tin(IV) dichloride C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₄ Cl ₂ Sn	yellow	22.19 (22.31)	13.51 (13.32)	50.14 (49.66)	2.90 (2.65)	—
5a.	-do- ammonia adduct C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₄ Cl ₂ Sn.4NH ₃	yellow	20.02 (19.78)	11.64 (11.82)	—	—	9.56 (9.34)
5b.	-do- methylamine adduct C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₄ Cl ₂ Sn.2CH ₃ NH ₂	yellow	20.03 (19.94)	11.74 (11.91)	—	—	4.38 (4.71)
6.	Bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydato) tin(IV) dibromide. C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₄ Br ₂ Sn	—	19.28 (19.12)	25.95 (25.74)	—	—	—
7.	Bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydato) tin(IV) diiodide. C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₄ I ₂ Sn	—	16.42 (16.61)	35.58 (35.50)	—	—	—
8.	Bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydato) tin(II) C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₄ Sn	yellow	25.92 (25.74)	—	56.87 (57.29)	3.34 (3.06)	—
9.	Mono(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydato) titanium(IV) triisopropoxide C ₂₀ H ₂₈ O ₅ Ti Mol. wt. deted. in benzene 380 (396 for monomer).	red	12.18 (12.09)	—	60.34 (60.61)	7.41 (7.11)	—
10.	Bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydato) titanium(IV) diisopropoxide C ₂₈ H ₂₈ O ₆ Ti Mol. wt. deted. 498 in benzene (508 for monomer).	red brown	9.62 (9.42)	—	66.88 (66.15)	5.82 (5.55)	—
11.	Mono(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydato) monoisopropoxy oxotitanium(IV) C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₄ Ti Mol. wt. determined in benzene-1122 (1176 for tetramer).	red	16.32 (16.29)	—	56.90 (57.18)	5.12 (4.80)	—

Figures in parentheses are calculated values.
Molecular weights were determined ebullioscopically.

temperature. The direct reaction of stannic tetrachloride with the ligand yielded the addition compound $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{L}$.

The ammonia and methylamine adducts were obtained by treatment of suspension of the chloro complexes in ether (at 5° – 10°) with the gaseous base. The complexes were dried *in vacuo* at room temperature.

The starting materials were purified before use. Pure and dry solvents were used. Nitrogen blanket was used in the experiments wherever necessary.

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